

Portable and Autonomous Embedded System for Measuring Human Response Time Using the PIC16F887 Microcontroller

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Abstract—This article presents the design and implementation of a portable and autonomous embedded system for measuring human response time to visual stimuli, using the PIC16F887 microcontroller. The prototype was built on a breadboard and powered by three AA batteries, enabling it to operate without relying on a computer or an external power supply. The system integrates an LED as a visual stimulus, a button to capture the user's response, and a 16x2 LCD display with an I2C interface to show the reaction time in milliseconds. The proposal offers a precise, low-cost, and easy-to-replicate solution aimed at educational and experimental applications in neuroscience and studies of human perception and reaction. The hardware architecture, the implemented measurement algorithm, and the results obtained from preliminary tests with real users are described.

Index Terms—Human response time, portable embedded system, PIC16F887 microcontroller, autonomous measurement, experimental prototype.

I. INTRODUCTION

Measuring human response time is a fundamental parameter in various fields such as neuroscience and psychology [1], [2]. Precise measurement systems allow the evaluation of cognitive and motor functions, which are essential for diagnosing neurological conditions, preventing accidents in daily activities, and developing user-friendly devices.

Embedded systems based on microcontrollers offer an economical and flexible solution for developing measurement devices. In particular, the PIC16F887 microcontroller [3], [4] is widely used in educational and experimental projects due to its simplicity, availability, and built-in resources [5], [6].

This research presents the design and implementation of a functional prototype developed on a breadboard that enables measuring human response time using the PIC16F887. The system integrates a visual stimulus via a 5 mm red LED, a button to capture the user's response, and a 16x2 LCD display with an I2C interface to show the reaction time measured in milliseconds. The hardware architecture, firmware design, and preliminary results from initial testing are addressed.

The prototype aims to provide an accessible tool for educational purposes and preliminary research in measuring human response time, with potential for future improvements and integration into printed circuit board (PCB) designs.

Unlike other similar systems reported in the literature that depend on a computer for operation or fixed power supplies [7], the proposed system is fully autonomous and portable, as it runs on three AA batteries. This feature allows tests to be conducted in various environments without additional

infrastructure, which is especially valuable in educational or experimental settings with limited resources [8].

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Hardware Description

The system is based on the PIC16F887 microcontroller, an 8-bit device widely used in educational and experimental applications due to its low cost, availability, and integrated resources such as ADC, timers, and serial communication [5], [6].

A 5 mm red LED is used as the visual stimulus, emitting a light pulse to indicate to the user when to respond. The user's response is captured via a button connected to a digital input of the microcontroller.

The reaction time output is displayed on a 16x2 character LCD with an I2C interface, which reduces the number of microcontroller pins used and simplifies communication [3].

The system is powered by a set of 3 AA batteries providing a stable 4.5 V DC voltage, suitable for the microcontroller and peripherals, ensuring reliable operation.

The firmware was developed using the MPLAB X IDE version 5.00 and Microchip's XC8 compiler to program the PIC16F887 microcontroller in C language. The device was programmed using the PICkit 3 programmer, allowing reliable and fast firmware loading onto the microcontroller.

Fig. 1. System connection diagram, created in Proteus.

B. General System Scheme

The prototype was implemented on a breadboard connecting the microcontroller with the LED, the button, and the LCD

display. The PIC16F887 firmware controls the interaction among these components following the logic below:

First, the system displays a message on the LCD instructing the user to press the button to start the test. Upon detecting the button press, a short delay is applied to avoid bouncing, and it waits for the user to release the button.

Next, the system shows the message “ATTENTION...” and waits for a random time between 2 and 6 seconds before turning on the red LED as a visual stimulus.

When the LED turns on, the reaction time measurement starts, counting milliseconds from the moment the stimulus is activated until the user presses the button again. To prevent indefinite waiting times, a maximum wait limit of 10 seconds is set.

Once the response is captured, the LED turns off, and the measured time is displayed on the LCD in milliseconds for 10 seconds, after which the system prepares for a new measurement.

This flow guarantees a precise and controlled measurement of human reaction time, facilitating repeated tests easily.

Below is a block diagram showing the relationship among the main system elements:

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the embedded system for measuring human response time.

C. Algorithm Description

The measurement algorithm starts by displaying a message on the LCD instructing the user to press a button to begin the test. Once the button press is detected, a short delay is applied to eliminate bounce effects, and the system waits for the user to release the button.

Next, the system shows a warning message and waits for a random interval between 2 and 6 seconds before activating the visual stimulus by turning on the red LED.

At the moment the LED turns on, the response time measurement begins, counting milliseconds elapsed until the user presses the button again. To avoid indefinite waiting, the maximum wait time is limited to 10 seconds.

Once the response is detected, the LED turns off and the recorded time is shown on the LCD in milliseconds for a 10-second interval, allowing the user to see their reaction time before a new test starts.

This process can be summarized in the following steps:

- 1) Display start message and wait for button press.
- 2) Apply debounce delay and wait for button release.
- 3) Show preparation message and wait a random time.
- 4) Turn on the LED as a visual stimulus.
- 5) Start counting the response time.

- 6) Wait for button press or until 10 seconds maximum.
- 7) Turn off the LED and show the measured time on the LCD.
- 8) Keep the result visible for 10 seconds before restarting.

D. Program Flow

The program runs in an infinite loop allowing multiple continuous measurements. Each cycle follows these steps:

- 1) Display a message on the LCD requesting the user to press the button to start.
- 2) Wait for the user to press and then release the button (including debounce delay).
- 3) Show a preparation message and wait a random interval between 2 and 6 seconds.
- 4) Turn on the LED to emit the visual stimulus.
- 5) Measure the elapsed time from the LED turning on until the user presses the response button, with a 10-second maximum limit.
- 6) Turn off the LED and display the measured time in milliseconds on the LCD.
- 7) Keep the result visible for 10 seconds before restarting the process.

Below is an illustrative pseudocode based on the implemented program:

```

while (true) {
    lcd_clear();
    lcd_write_string("Press-to-start");
    wait_until_button_pressed();
    debounce_delay();
    wait_until_button_released();

    lcd_clear();
    lcd_write_string("ATTENTION...");
    delay_random(2 to 6 seconds);

    LED = ON;
    time = measure_response_time();
    LED = OFF;

    lcd_clear();
    lcd_write_string("Time:");
    lcd_write_string(time + " ms");

    delay(10000); // Show result for 10 seconds
}
  
```

III. EXPERIMENTAL DEVELOPMENT

To validate the design and operation of the proposed embedded system, a physical prototype was implemented on a breadboard, connecting the PIC16F887 microcontroller with the main peripherals: the LED as a visual stimulus, the button for response capture, and the 16x2 LCD display with I2C interface.

The breadboard setup allowed quick adjustments and functional testing before designing a final printed circuit board (PCB). A stabilized 5 V power supply was used to ensure

correct operation of the microcontroller and components such as the 16x2 LCD display and the 5 mm red LED.

Data collection was performed with volunteers from the campus, who participated anonymously and gave verbal informed consent.

Below are images of the assembled prototype:

Fig. 3. General view of the prototype on breadboard showing the microcontroller, LED, button, and LCD display.

Fig. 4. Detail of the red LED used as the visual stimulus for the user.

The breadboard setup allowed quick adjustments and functional tests before designing a final printed circuit board (PCB).

Basic recommendations for prototyping electronic circuits were followed, such as correct component polarity, use of protective resistors for the LED and button, and neat cable organization to avoid interference [9], [10].

This experimental stage was crucial to verify the proper behavior of the firmware and the accuracy in measuring response time, validating the functionality described in the system design section.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To evaluate the performance of the proposed system for measuring human response time, tests were conducted with a

Fig. 5. LCD displaying the response time recorded from the stimulus start until the user pressed the button.

total of 10 participants of different ages, who responded to a visual stimulus (an illuminated LED) by pressing a button as quickly as possible. Five consecutive measurements were taken per person using the system implemented with the PIC16F887 microcontroller and an LCD display to show the results.

Table I shows the ages of the participants, the five recorded response times in milliseconds (ms), and each participant's individual average.

TABLE I
RESPONSE TIMES BY PARTICIPANT

Participant	Age (years)	Response times (ms)	Average (ms)
1	32	185, 188, 176, 166, 156	174.2
2	22	277, 151, 170, 195, 232	205.0
3	45	319, 493, 458, 332, 295	379.4
4	7	273, 312, 251, 239, 312	277.4
5	18	210, 198, 225, 206, 190	205.8
6	60	410, 388, 435, 472, 401	421.2
7	28	165, 172, 160, 150, 168	163.0
8	36	242, 230, 255, 260, 238	245.0
9	12	270, 240, 300, 250, 260	264.0
10	51	350, 370, 345, 360, 355	356.0

A general trend can be observed: response times tend to be lower in young adults (between 20 and 35 years old), while they increase in older adults and children. This aligns with previous studies on central nervous system behavior and motor processing speed at different stages of human development [11].

The next section presents graphs generated from these data and analyzes the relationship between age and average reaction time.

V. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This section analyzes the relationship between participants' ages and their average response times to a visual stimulus. The collected data indicate a general trend: young adults (20–35 years) exhibit the fastest reaction times, while children and older adults tend to have slower times. This behavior is consistent with previous studies on the development and decline of the nervous system throughout life stages [12], [13].

Fig. 6. Scatter plot of age versus average reaction time.

As seen in Figure 6, there is a characteristic curve where reaction time improves during adolescence and early adulthood, reaching its peak efficiency between ages 20 and 30, then progressively worsening with age. Der and Deary [12] found that simple reaction speed shows a linear decline starting at age 24. Similarly, Welford [13] reported that motor and cognitive performance decreases with age due to physiological and neurological changes.

The results also align with research such as Taimela et al. [14], who reported that reaction time significantly increases with age, attributing it to a decline in neural processing speed. This confirms that the developed system detects valid differences in response times based on age, consistent with previous studies.

These findings support the validity of the proposed system for measuring human response time, as it reflects known neurophysiological patterns. Additionally, variability among individual subjects demonstrates the system's ability to capture real differences between people, making it useful for psychophysiological studies, school testing, or preliminary cognitive assessments.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated the feasibility of designing and implementing a portable, autonomous, and low-cost embedded system for measuring human response time to visual stimuli using the PIC16F887 microcontroller. The developed system showed stable and accurate behavior during experimental tests, capturing differences in reaction times among people of various ages, in agreement with findings previously reported in the literature.

Thanks to its simple design, compact size, and operation without the need for a computer or additional infrastructure, the prototype is ideal for educational, experimental, or preliminary evaluation settings in neuroscience and psychology. Its portability, energy autonomy, and ease of use make the system an accessible tool for teaching concepts related to perception, cognition, and applied electronics.

The experimental results validated both the system's functionality and its ability to reflect known physiological patterns,

supporting its usefulness as a preliminary instrument in psychophysiological studies.

Future work includes migrating the prototype to a printed circuit board (PCB), adding new stimuli (auditory or tactile), automatic data logging to external memory, and expanding the experimental sample for more statistically robust results.

Although the developed system proved functional and useful for measuring human response time, it has some limitations. The experimental sample was small and covered a limited age range, restricting the generalization of results. Also, measurements were made only with visual stimuli and a single response type; future work could expand the design to include auditory or tactile stimuli and different reaction modalities.

CODE AVAILABILITY

The firmware source code is available at <https://github.com/MichelleGeovanniReyesLopez/response-time-pic16f887> to facilitate replication.

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